

MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

Virtual Gallery

www.matilde-migration.eu

MATILDE has received
funding from the European
Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation
programme under grant
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Call: H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2019

Work Programmes:

H2020-EU.3.6.1.1. The mechanisms to promote smart, sustainable and inclusive growth

H2020-EU.3.6.1.2. Trusted organisations, practices, services and policies that are necessary to build resilient, inclusive, participatory, open and creative societies in Europe, in particular taking into account migration, integration and demographic change

Deliverable 7.16

MATILDE Virtual Gallery

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Version: 29.09.2021

Link: <https://matilde-migration.eu/virtual-gallery-2/>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5529663

How to cite: *MATILDE Virtual Gallery*. 2021. Deliverable D7.16. DOI:
10.5281/zenodo.5529663

This document was produced under the terms and conditions of Grant Agreement No. 870831 for the European Commission. It does not necessarily reflect the view of the European Union and in no way anticipates the Commission's future policy in this area.

What is it?

The deliverable is the D. 7.16 MATILDE Virtual Gallery, part of the task 7.5 Communication towards the General Public. It represents the virtual exhibition, which is embedded on the project official website. The Gallery is a shared space where we publish the photos collected during the activity of the Project, for example, the action-research activities, the photo contest and other input received from partners and amateurs. It is a 'living space' that will be updated, as project activities progress.

The aim of the Gallery is to provide visibility to the project activities and to the best practices developed in rural and mountain areas. In this regard, the Gallery will be maintained and enriched with the artistic inputs to support and share the contents with the public and to promote public awareness about migration in the inner areas. In order to target a diversified, non-specialist audience, the contents of the Gallery will also be intended to support and share the communication and the dissemination project channel, making available textual and visual contents through the social media.

The gallery will be implemented through:

- the virtual catalogue of innovative integration practices (D. 5.6);
- the pictures collected during the photo contest on migration impact in the local territory (task 7.5.4);
- the pictures taken during action research, the involvement of photographers and the events promoted by the partners.

These contents of the Gallery will be disseminated via social media.

- the Gallery will be available until March 2023. After that, it is possible to upload the pictures to the Zenodo repository, where they will be available permanently, under specific licenses.

Finally, the direct link to the online gallery is:

<https://art.kunstmatrix.com/apps/artspaces/?external=true&splashscreen=true&language=en&uid=66719&exhibition=7810989>

Screenshots

Screenshot 1. Gallery home page

Screenshot 2. Photo area of Bulgaria

Screenshot 3. Photo area of Finland

Screenshot 4. Picture description from the photo area of Germany

